

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B047
Date: 02 Sep 2004
Take Off 08:16:19
Landing: 13:15:22
Flight Time 4h59m03

Trials Instructions: ADRIEX – flight over northern Adriatic and along the Po Valley.

Operating Area: Northern Adriatic and Po Valley, N Italy

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Foster	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Alan Roberts	Directflight
3	Mission Scientist 1	Jim Haywood	Met Office
4	Flight Manager	Maureen Smith	FAAM
5	Dropsondes	Steve Devereau	FAAM
6	Core Chemistry / CCM2	Doug Anderson	FAAM
7	CVI	Paul James	FAAM
8	VACC / TDL / PAN	Jim McQuaid	Leeds University
9	Cloud Physics	Martyn Pickering	Met Office
10	SWS	Andy Wilson	Met Office
11	Filters	Paola Formenti	CNRS/University of Paris 12
12	AMS	Paul Williams	UMIST
13	Nephelometer / PSAP	Jolene Cook	Reading University
14	Mission Scientist 2	Simon Osborne	Met Office
15	Mission Scientist 3	Elisabeth Ostrom	Met Office
16	Mission Scientist 3	Ellie Highwood	Reading University
17	CCM	Sue Angold	Directflight
18			
19			
20			

Flight Track:

B047 Track 02-SEP-04

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B047
 Date: 02/09/2004
 Project: ADRIEX
 Location: Treviso

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
063000		UBBRs	-.10 kft	020	Covers removed
073243		INU	-.10 kft	020	To Navigate
081619		T/O	3.1 kft	201	Treviso
082012		Videos	4.9 kft	131	FFC & DFC
083120	083643	Profile 1	50' - 3.8 kft	150	500fpm to FL30
083655	083850	Profile 1	4.0 - 6.0 kft	152	Interrupt
084026	084822	Profile 1	6.1 - 14.9 kft	355	1000fpm
085230		Sonde	15.0 kft	223	Launch 01, T&H failed
090041		Sonde	15.0 kft	226	Launch 02
090154	090414	Profile 2	15.0 - 13.1 kft	143	
090414	091001	Run 1	13.1 - 13.0 kft	138	Into Sun
091209	091948	Profile 3	13.0 - 5.9 kft	318	Down Sun, 1000fpm
092303	093228	Run 2	5.9 kft	143	Into Sun
093408	093547	Profile 4	5.9 - 4.9 kft	328	1000fpm Down Sun
093547	094348	Run 3	4.9 kft	324	Down Sun at 5000ft
094442	094611	Profile 5	4.9 - 3.9 kft	239	1000fpm, Into Sun
094653	095649	Run 4	3.9 kft	153	Into Sun
095841	100711	Profile 6	4.0 - 100 ft	339	1000fpm, Down Sun
101155	102157	Run 5.1	100 ft	159	Into Sun
102503	103436	Run 5.2	100ft	343	Down Sun
103646	103828	Orbit 1	800 ft	207	38deg RH, 210deg
103940	104118	Orbit 2	800 ft	276	start 270
104256	104435	Orbit 3	800 ft	112	start 120
104524	104701	Orbit 4	800 ft	174	start 180
105551	105731	Orbit 5	900 ft	345	38deg, RH, start 360
105845	110021	Orbit 6	900 ft	091	start 090
110125	110301	Orbit 7	900 ft	164	start 180
110357	110538	Orbit 8	900 ft	277	start 270
110906		PSAP	1000 ft	099	Change Filter
111149	112149	Run 6	1000 ft	181	Into Sun, 1000ft
112317	112711	Profile 7	1000 - 3.8 kft	001	Down Sun
112712	113333	Run 7	3.8 - 3.9 kft	008	Down Sun
112839		Videos	3.8 kft	008	Change tapes
113508	113620	Profile 8	3.9 - 4.9 kft	186	1000fpm
113620	114513	Run 8	4.9 kft	192	
114955	115113	Profile 9	4.9 - 5.8 kft	016	
115113	115810	Run 9	5.8 - 5.9 kft	019	Down Sun
120505	121148	Profile 10	5.9 - 11.9 kft	204	1000fpm Held low by ATC
121339	121941	Run 10	12.0 kft	033	Down Sun
122519		Sonde	12.0 kft	264	Launch 03, on RFC
122842	123211	Profile 11	12.0 - 8.7 kft	151	1000fpm
123406	124000	Profile 11	8.7 - 2.9 kft	336	1000fpm
124142	124502	Profile 11	2.9 - 1.4 kft	160	500fpm from 3000ft
124639	124935	Profile 11	1.3 - 50'	343	
125149	125255	Orbit 9	0.66 - 1.1 kft	001	53deg RH, start 360
125402	125509	Orbit 10	1.1 - 0.85 kft	125	start 150
125607	125713	Orbit 11	0.95 - 0.87 kft	226	start 240
125852	125858	Orbit 12	0.92 - 0.90 kft	198	start 360
125815	125921	Orbit 12	0.83 kft	352	
131522		Land	-.08 kft	024	Treviso

B047 Track 02-SEP-04

FAAM Sortie Brief

Flight Number: B047

Date 2nd September 2004

Purpose: ADRIEX flight over northern Adriatic and along the Po Valley.

Weather: Predominantly cloud-free. Heavy pollution preferred.

Flight Pattern:

- 1) Take off Treviso 0800z.
- 2) Transit to point A at low level (10mins).
- 3) Interrupted profile ascent from 50' to FL150 over point A (Ocean Tower at 45°18'51"N,12°30'29"E) (30mins).
- 4) Dropsonde #1 at FL150
- 5) Stacked profile descent with 4 SLRs of 10-minute duration orientated into- and down- sun at different levels to be determined by the aircraft scientist over point A (90mins).
- 6) Set of banked orbits over point A at the solar zenith angle (~45°) at 500ft (100mins).
- 7) Holding pattern for 10minutes (110mins).
- 8) Set of banked orbits over point A at the solar zenith angle (~45°) at 500ft (120mins).
- 9) Transit out at low level to a position north of point F at the power plant (44°36'N, 12°12'E) (125mins).
- 10) Series of 2x7min runs orientated cross-wind moving away from point F at 500ft (140mins).
- 11) Profile ascent from 500ft to 3000ft towards point A (150mins).
- 12) SLR at 3000ft from A to point B (44°30'N,12°00'E) (165mins).
- 13) SLR at 3000ft from B to point C at Soave (45°25'N,11°15'E) (185mins).
- 14) SLR at 3000ft from C to point D at Reggio Nell Emilia (44°42'N,10°32'E) (200mins).
- 15) SLR at 3000ft from from D to point E at (45°30'N,10°00'E) (215mins).
- 16) Profile ascent to FL150 from point E to point D (230mins).
- 17) Profile descent from FL150 to 3000ft from point D to point C (245mins) .
- 18) SLR at 3000ft from point C to point B (265mins).
- 19) SLR at 3000ft from point B to point A (280mins).
- 20) Interrupted profile ascent from 50ft to FL150 over point A (295mins).
- 21) Dropsonde #2 at FL150.
- 22) Recover to Treviso (305mins).

Point A (Ocean Tower)	45°18'51"N,12°30'29"E
Point B	44°30'N,12°00'E
Point C (Soave)	45°25'N,11°15'E
Point D (Reggio Nell Emilia)	44°42'N,10°32'E
Point E	45°30'N,10°00'E
Point F (Power plant)	44°36'N, 12°12'E

Aircraft Scientist de-brief sheet

B047

2nd September 2004-09-04

Weather conditions:

High pressure centred over Poland, central pressure ~1022 mb, bringing very slack easterly flow at the surface. Flow aloft northerly to westerly, about 5 kts. Stable conditions in the Adriatic. Cloud free conditions prevalent.

Flight aims:

To conduct in-situ and radiometric measurements of Po valley pollution over the northern Adriatic Sea.

Summary of the flight:

A very successful flight was conducted over the northern Adriatic in conjunction with the instrumented Venice ocean tower (point Alpha). Met conditions were ideal for radiation observations as there was totally cloud-free conditions in the operating region. The initial profile ascent from 50' to FL150 showed the main pollution layer to lie between ~4000' and ~7000', although light pollution was measured up to ~FL100. 2 sondes were dropped from FL150 (sonde #1 was faulty). The pollution from above looked like a cirrus shield ! A set of stacked straight and level runs was carried out during the profile descent at the following heights and orientations, working south of point A:

- (i) FL130, above pollution, into Sun
- (ii) 6000', in pollution, into Sun
- (iii) 5000', in pollution, down Sun
- (iv) 4000', base of pollution, into Sun
- (v) Two 100' runs, within marine boundary layer, into and down Sun

Within the pollution layer, PCASP concs (discounting bins 1-3) were ~500/cc, CN concs were ~3000/cc, CO mixing ratios ~ 130 ppbv. Aerosol characteristics were very different in the MBL (which was ~700' deep): CN concs were up to 30,000/cc. The localised 'industrial plant' plume was sampled during the 100ft run. There was generally a lot of structure on the CN and CO during the 100ft run; the PCASP showed less structure. Two sets of four 38deg orbits were then carried out at 800', at the boundary between the MBL and free trop, over point A. This way, we isolated the elevated pollution above from the MBL aerosol in radiometric terms. The SWS filters were changed between the sets of orbits. A second set of runs was carried out during a profile ascent at the following levels:

- (i) 1000', above MBL but below EPL, into Sun
- (ii) 4000', base of EPL, down Sun
- (iii) 5000', EPL, into Sun
- (iv) 6000', EPL, down Sun
- (v) FL120, above EPL

We were restricted to FL120 due to air traffic reasons. Another sonde was dropped at FL120. A profile descent was then made to 50'. The aerosol structure remained fairly constant in the vertical throughout the flight. We had time at the end to carry out a set of four orbits over point A, banked at 53deg, right wing down. This was $\theta_{szen} + 10deg.$, so that we can extend the scattering angle further.

Instrument problems:

Nephelometer: display of data shows very strange structure. This has been shown to be due to bit 10 (of the 16 bits) reading zero constantly. For the next flight, the data will be logged directly to a PC in addition to the DRS. Meanwhile, the problem will be investigated.

PSAP: data logging still directly onto a laptop due to a recording error. It would seem that the neph/PSAP/filters rack is suspect.

PCASP: bins 1 to 3 to be discounted.

FSSP: over heating problem. Post-flight inspection of unit showed a cable melted during the flight!

S. R. Osborne.

Aircraft Scientist's Log

winds!!

S. R. OSBORNE

Flight No **B.047**
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Date 02/09/04

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
0816					T/O TRENTO AIRPORT FUEL PRE-T/O RUNWAY 4000 / 1930 / 3730 / 2T
			0 → T/O.		Whitish haze; cloud on hills to right Quite poor vis. Main pollution base? Pea Souper!
082250		4000'			Overcast (v. poor vis) Clear above + below for cloud. A few white caps S2?
0829		5000'			overcast ^{In} descent. Main layer seems above us now
08324	PIA	50'	149	45.2 12.5	Start profile ascent. Better vis at surface. Plume greyish to over right. Clear skies all around.
083330	PIA	1500'			vis poorer ahead now. winds ^W 2/300
083540					Above chimney
083850	PIA	6000'			Interrupt profile RASP ~ 350/40
084025	PIA	6000'	352	44.9 12.9	re-start profile ascent Thick aerosol to our right
	PIA	7000'			Digging out - Neph down - clearer above aerosol layer here
084300	PIA	9000'			CO ₂ levelled off. CO ₂ 72 ppbv
084920	PI	72150	350	45.4 11.9	End profile ascent -

Aircraft Scientist's Log

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
					Some cloud over land. Cu
				1/220°	winds @ FL150.
085233	-	FL150		45.3 12.6	Release DROPSONDE #1
					DROPSONDE defective
	-	FL150			CN ~ 700/c. No Alaskan plane? PI re-up. ^{good} Hydroprobe @ 700mb.
090041	-	FL150	226	45.3 12.5	SONDE #2 release
090152	P2↓	FL150	143	45.2 12.5	Start profile descent. White haze ahead.
090413	P2/P1	FL130	137	45.1 12.6	End profile / start ^(SLP) run above EPL Ci appearance to cloud below.
091001	P1	FL130	136	44.8 13.0	End straight + level run above EPL winds ^{m/s} 03/13°
091210	P3↓	FL130↓	318	44.8 13.1	Start profile descent 1000ft/min.
	P3↓	FL130↓			winds ^{m/s} 01/351°
	↓	9000'↓			TOP of weak cloud CN/70
	P3↓	7200'↓			Big hits on Repl. Thunder cloud. Poor vis near.
091947	P3↓	6000'↓	320	45.2 12.6	End profile descent-
092304	P2→	6000'	144	45.2 12.5	Start run in EPL. CN ~ 2400/c. PRRP ~ 500/c ^{uncorr.}
					PRAP 2.9 x 10 ⁶ m ⁻¹ . Altk units on v. Diffuse white haze ^{horizontal???}
					ahead. 0.67 m ² x 6L03
					Zero clouds. 108 CO
093239	P2	6000'	144	44.8 13.0	End SLP in EPL.

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 Date **02/09/04**

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
093408	P4↓	6000↓	329	44.8 13.1	Start profile descent. 1000 ft/min. brownish tinged aerosol ahead.
093547	P4/R3	5000↓	325	44.9 13.0	End profile / start run in iPL CN ~ 3000/cc. PASP ~ 500/cc. CVA PASP ~ 20/cc. in plume greyish
0739					Can see base of plume ahead. PASP ~ $3.6 \times 10^6 \text{ m}^{-1}$ Loosenes realistic
094226					Structure in aerosol. Note in particular
094347	R3	5000'	325	45.3 12.6	End run in iPL down - Sur. [SWS abs. from aerosol in near-ER]
094442	P5↓	5000'	239	45.3 12.5	Start profile descent @ 1000 ft/min
094607	P5→	4000'	209	45.3 12.4	End profile descent
094647	R4→	4000'→	152	45.2 12.5	Start SLR in iPL base CN ~ 2500/cc. CN ~ 2000/cc. PASP
095240					Abeam individual site. Plume detected on counters. CN ~ 4000/cc. CO peaked @ 130-140 ppt. VACE also increasing in plume.
095648	R4→	4000'	151	44.7 12.9	End run in iPL base. winds 03/245°
095840	P6↓	4000↓ 3500' 3000'	338	44.9 13.0	Start profile descent. 6000 ft. Base of plume main? CO/CN etc. 500 ft/min descent rate.

Aircraft Scientist's Log

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Date **02/09/00**

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
	P6 ↓	1600'	336		W/thing around Lure - localized
100517		500'			cn ~ 14,000/cc. SURL Phase?
					Neph high as well.
1006	P6 →	100'	337	45.2 12.7	end profile descent.
101154	RS	100'	159	45.2 12.4	Start SUR @ 100' INTO SUN
		100'			cn ~ 28,000/cc. CVC PERSP, 1000-1500/cc. 225C ~ 300/cc on VSEC RASP ~ 7.0 x 10 ⁶ m ⁻¹
101130	RS.1	100'	158	45.0 12.6	Abeam Power Plant tower
					PERSP ~ 400/cc (1-3 bins out SW)
10118	RS.1	100'			AMS running etc. near
					clear skies all around. SS2
10218	RS.1	100'	163	44.7 12.5	End Run into into -Sun
102504	RS.2	100'	343	44.7 12.6	Start SUR @ 100' ^{DOWN SUN} - SURL
					Neph fairly constant at this level.
					cn v. plume.
					CPSIVE ~ 15,000/cc
102830		100'			Abeam industrial site on our left.
					↳ cn counts rising, No RASP rises
					Some slips around
103400	RS.2	100'			Back into broad plume again
103434			345	45.2 12.4	(Man ship) End SUR
103602	OR	800'		45.2 12.4	Start orbits. flight ^(38°) very down
					over point ALPHA

103825 022 400'

End of rollout

Aircraft Scientist's Log

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
103939	02↓	800'		45.2 12.4	Start next orbit. Map dropping off → on SMC boundaries! Good! (N also) down to 4000 ft.
104118	02↓	800'			End & roll out to steady.
104256	03↓	800'			Start next orbit. $\theta_{span} = 38.19^\circ$ (Next visib again) → <u>own plane?</u>
104435	03↓	800'			End orbit & roll out
104524	04↓	800'		45.2 12.5	Start 4 th orbit, right links down
104700	04↓	800'		45.2 12.5	End 1 st set of orbits. Horiz. pattern follows
105550	05↓	900'		45.2 12.4	2 nd set of orbits @ 38° bank angle Totally clear here all around.
105730	05↓	900'			End. Ships still around.
105864	06↓	900'		45.3 12.5	Start orbit
110020	06↓	900'			End orbit & roll out.
110124	07↓	900'		45.2 12.5	Start orbit <u>second layer SMC visible here</u>
110300	07↓	900'			End orbit
110355	08↓	900'			Start last orbit (for now....) Further view fairly wide!
110557	08↓	900'		45.2 12.5	End orbits
111149	R6	1000'	180	45.2 12.7	Start SLR into Sun. Azim $\approx 183^\circ$.
115					Second wave visib in 10 th sec Latter or CPL ?!! SMC

Aircraft Scientist's Log

Oster + 10°

Flight No **B. 047**

Date **02/09/04**

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
11 21 48		1000'		44.6 12.7	End run just above SUR
11 23 20	P7↑	1000'	001	44.62.6	Start profile ascent
11 24 44		~1800'			Can see base of pollution cloud. → v. clear to the eye skies clear all around Good 'clear' slot here.
11 25 20		~2400'			
11 27 16	→ P7.	4000'	008	44.7 12.7	Start Run. in base of pollution Augs → 50% increase Next → diff Aug strum with Seem to be in front of main aerosol deck.
11 33 32	→ P7	4000'		45.3 12.8	End Run in base of pollution
11 35 05	P8↑	4000'	187	45.3 12.9	Start profile ascent
11 36 11	P8/R8	5000'	118	45.2 12.9	End profile / Start SUR PCASP ~ 400 cc. CN ~ 3500/cc
11 45 12	R8	5000'	195	44.6 12.7	End Run.
11 49 54	P9↑	5000'	016	44.7 12.6	Start profile ascent 1000 ft/min.
11 51 12	P9 P9→	6000'	019	44.8 12.7	End profile ascent / Start SUR
11 52					Next dropped off + CN CO ~ 100 ppbv. CN ~ 2000/cc end
11 59 08	→ P9	6000'	019	45.2 12.9	End SUR = pollution tops just! v. white. appearance $\tau \approx 0.3$ @ 0.8 km $w_0 \approx 0.76$ (converter's) RH amb $\approx 85\%$

Aircraft Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B...04T**

 Date **02/09/04**

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
120507	P10 [↑]	6000 [↑]	206	45.2 12.8	Start profile ascent.
120920		FL095			Lts of Cu tops above base
	P10 [↑]				Large ahead of us → overland
					White appearance to be pollution
					from here.
	P10 [↑]	FL100			Cloud just to our right.
121149	P10 [→]	FL120	205	44.8 12.5	End profile climb.
					Re-position for SLR.
121338	P10 [→]	FL120	032	44.8 12.6	Start profile S+L Run. above
					all ⁵⁰ cleared. ^{Small} Cu added to our right.
					Counters all v. low.
					just overland?
121940	P10 [→]	FL120	028	45.2 12.9	End SLR above E-PL
1222					So L here, maybe etc. death
					for BSLs etc.
122518	—	FL120	264	45.2 12.4	DROPSOUND #3 Released.
					Beautifully clear skies above.
122740		FL120			Deep Cu ahead (overland)
					↳ small cumil?
122842	P11 [↓]	FL020	151	45.1 12.5	Start profile descent.
123206	P11 [↓]	FL087	151	44.8 12.7	End 2p. 2knight profile descent
					CN n 8000m.
123405	P11 [↓]	FL087	336	44.9 12.7	Re-start profile descent with
					overland deck.
		FL086			getting more humid.

TOP of plume @ 2700 metres

Aircraft Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B.047**

 Date **07/07/04**

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
	P11 ↓	5500' ↓	332		Higher ^{signal} clouds on red / white etc. PASP ~ 500/cc.
124000	P11 →	3000' →	331	45.2 12.5	Interrupt profile descent to turn * N ₂ RH ~ 55% in IPL
124143	P11 ↓	3000' ↓	159	45.2 12.4	Le-start profile descent 500 ft/min
124500	P11 →	1500' →	150	45.0 12.6	Interrupt profile descent to turn below FPL
124639	P11 ↓	1500' ↓	344	45.1 12.6	Le-start profile descent to 50'
		600'			Totally void of all cloud. into SWL. → clear on neph sigs
		250'			NSF must change on -10 in SWL CN v. high here 15,000'/cc
124932	P11	50'	344	45.2 12.5	End profile descent @ 50' Ocean surface a few ships near tower
125149	09 ↓	1000'		45.3 12.4	Start orbit set. (230 kts)
125252	09 ↓	~1300' +1000'			End orbit.
125402	010 ↓	~1000'			Start orbit: check vert & descent rate. Q ₅₀₀ = 439°
125509	010 ↓	~1100'			End orbit.
125608	011 ↓	~1300'		45.2 12.5	Start orbit, PICAT wings down
125713	011 ↓	7000'			End orbit.
1258	012 ↓	1000'	an 360°	45	Start orbit. Q ₅₀₀ = 44°
125923	012 ↓	1050'			End orbit.

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B047

Date: 2/9/04

Operator: MAP

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G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
08:31:23	340		Laser problem	5							Start Profile 1 from 50'
08:33:12	240			5							FL010
08:34:36	260			5							FL020
08:35:59	320			10							FL030
08:36:58	300			10							FL040
08:37:40	350			10							FL050
08:38:49	300			10							FL060
08:41:20	160			5							FL070
08:42:11	100			3							FL080
08:43:20	50			2							FL090
08:44:15	5										FL100
08:44:59	1										FL110
08:46:03	2										FL120
08:47:00	1										FL130
08:47:39	2										FL140
08:48:23	2										End of Profile 1 @ FL150
09:01:54	5										Start Profile 2 @ FL150
09:03:07	10										FL140
09:04:19											End of P2 Start Run 1 @ FL130
09:05:00	20										
09:07:00	20										
09:09:00	6										
09:10:01											End of Run 1
09:12:12	20										Start Profile 3 from FL130
09:13:35	10										FL120
09:14:35	5										FL110
09:15:23	10										FL100
09:16:27	115			2							FL090
09:17:30	150										FL080
09:18:30	480			5							FL070
09:19:50	450			5							End of Profile 3 @ FL060
09:23:05											Start Run 2 @ FL060

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B047

Date: 2/9/04

Operator: MAP

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G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
09:24:00	370			10							
09:26:00	300										
09:28:00	310										
09:30:00	300										
09:32:00	370										
09:32:28											End of Run 2
09:34:08											Start Profile 4 from FL060
09:35:48											End of P4 Start Run 3 @ 5000'
09:36:00	400			10							
09:38:00	400			5							
09:40:00	400			5							
09:42:00	530			5							
09:43:48											End of Run 3
09:44:00											Start Profile 5 @ 5000'
09:46:08											End of Profile 5 @ 4000'
09:46:53											Start Run 4 @ 4000'
09:47:00	330			5							
09:49:00	310			5							
09:51:00	420			5							
09:53:00	380			15							
09:55:00	530			15							
09:57:50											End of Run 4
09:58:41											Start Profile 6 from 4000'
10:00:26	350			10							3000'
10:02:20	420			8							2000'
10:03:47	240			8							1000'
10:07:11											End of Profile 6 @ 100'
10:11:55											Start Run 5.1 @ 100'
10:12:00	350			8							
10:14:00	350			8							
10:16:00	400			8							
10:18:00	400			8							

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B047

Date: 2/9/04

Operator: MAP

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G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
10:20:00	360			10							
10:21:57											End of Run 5.1
10:24:07											Start Run 5.2 @ 100'
10:26:00	400			5							
10:28:00	420			5							
10:30:00	380			5							
10:32:00	350			5							
10:34:39											End of run
10:36:46											Start Orbits @ 800'
10:47:03											End of Orbits (4)
10:55:57											Start Orbits @ 800'
11:05:38											End of Orbits PCASP heaters OFF
11:11:49											Start Run 6 @ 1000'
11:12:00	220			5							
11:14:00	260			5							
11:16:00	250			5							
11:18:00	340			5							
11:20:00	400			8							
11:21:51											End of Run 6
11:23:17											Start Profile 7 from 1000'
11:24:49	340			8							2000'
11:26:21	360			10							3000'
11:27:15											End of P7 Start Run 7 @ 4000'
11:28:00	420			10							
11:30:00	420			8							
11:32:00	410			8							
11:33:33											End of Run 7
11:35:06											Start Profile 8 from 4000'
11:36:20											End of P8 Start Run 8 @ 5000'
11:37:01	400			10							
11:39:00	400			15							
11:41:00	550			10							

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B047

Date: 2/9/04

Operator: MAP

Page 4 of 5

G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
11:43:00	530			20							
11:45:15	430			20							End of Run 8
11:49:55	400			10							Start Profile 9 from 5000'
11:51:18	350			10							End of P9 Start Run 9 @ FL060
11:52:00	400			10							
11:54:00	360			10							
11:56:00	330			5							
11:58:00	320			5							
11:58:10											End of Run 9
12:05:08											Start P10 From FL060
12:06:34	300			5							FL070
12:07:35	110			1							FL080
12:08:40	35			1							FL090
12:09:43	3										FL100
12:10:46	5										FL110
12:11:50	3										End of Profile 10 @ FL120
12:13:42											Start Run 10 @ FL120
12:14:00	1										
12:16:00	4										
12:18:00	4										
12:19:45											End of Run 10
12:28:45	2										Start Profile 11 from FL120
12:30:01	16										FL110
12:30:55	30										FL100
12:31:55	80										FL090
12:34:57	160			1							FL080
12:35:59	100			1							FL070
12:37:01	220			1							FL060
12:38:03	500			5							FL050
12:39:00	600			5							FL040
12:40:00	680			5							3000'
12:43:45	300			5							2000'

FAAM Dropsonde Flight Log

Flight No.	B047	Date	02/09/2004
Page No.	1 of 1	Operator	Steve Devereau

GMT	Sonde No.	Event	Comments
		<i>e.g. launch, splashdown</i>	<i>e.g. wind data? PTH data? Lat/Long</i>
08:52:29	01	Launch	45.3141N 12.5093E.
	01	Launch	Temperature and RH data (both RH sensors) failed on launch
08:59:29	01	splashdown	45.31558N 12.51372E
	01	Data to SDB	Data SATCOM'd to SDB
09:00:40	02	Launch	45.3152N 12.5039E
	02		Good drop
09:07:02	02	splashdown	45.31842N 12.51087E
	02	Data to SDB	Data SATCOM'd to SDB
12:25:21	03	Launch	45.31150N 12.50570E
	03		Good drop
12:30:38	03	splashdown	45.31371N 12.51538E
	03	Data to SDB	Data SATCOM'd to SDB
12:25:30	04	Launch	45.31060N 12.49130E
	04		Good drop of old Rev B sonde for comparison with 03
12:30:39	04	splashdown	45.31280N 12.49751E

SWS/SHIMS PRE-FLIGHT LOG		Date	02/9/04	Flight	B 047
Operator(s)	A. Wilson		Campaign	ADRIEX	
Departure	081600 Z		Arrival	131500 Z	

Physical system setup

Module Number <i>serial</i>	Connection(e.g.SWS nir, SHIMS upper)
0	SWS NIR
27581	SWS VIS

System functionality check After system stabilizes

PC to DRS Time error	$t_{PC} = t_{DRS} +$	0 Secs	at time	060000 Z
Freezer temp				

SWS FLIGHT LOG SHEET

Flight # **B 047** Date **02/09/04** Operator(s) **A. Wilson** log page **2** of **3**

Time	Run id	Alt/FL	Mirr Pos	Int Times		Remarks
				Vis	NIR	

101155	R5.1	100ft	46°F			into sun run. Zenith 39.8. Pitch 7°
102157	R5.1	100ft	46°F		Auto	end of R5.1
102503	R5.2	100ft	31°A		Auto.	Down sun run
103436	R5.2	100ft	31°A			end of run 5.2
103646	orbit 1	800ft	6°F			38° right to wing down.
1038	---	800ft	6°F	10	10	end
103940	--- 2	800ft	6°F	10	10	start orbit 2
1041	--- 2	800ft	6°F	10	10	end orbit 2
104256	--- 3	800ft	6°F	10	10	start orbit 3
	--- 3	800ft	6°F	15	30	end orbit 3
104528	--- 4	800ft	6°F	15	30	start orbit 4
104701	--- 4	800ft	6°F	15	30	end orbit 4
						Filters removed.
105551	orbit 5	800ft	6°F	10	10	start orbit 5 38° Right Wing down.
105731	--- 5	800ft	6°F	10	10	end orbit
105845	--- 6	800ft	6°F	10	10	start orbit 6
110021	--- 6	800ft	6°F	10	10	end orbit 6.
110125	--- 7	800ft	6°F	10	10	start 7
110301	7	800ft	6°F	10	10	end 7
110357	--- 8	800ft	6°F	10	10	start 8
110538	--- 8	800ft	6°F	10	10	end 8
111149	R6	1000ft				
111700		1000ft	43°F		Auto	Filters ND3 re-fitted for into & Down Sun runs.
112149	R6	1000ft	43°F		Auto	end of R6.
112317	P7	1000ft	30°A		Auto	start P7 → 4000ft
112712	P7	4000ft	30°A		Auto	end P7
	R7	4000ft	31°A		Auto.	start R7 down sun run
113340	R7	4000ft	31°A		Auto	end R7
113508	P8	4000ft	46°F		Auto	start P8
113620	P8	5000ft	46°F		Auto	end P8 @ 5000ft
	R8	5000ft	~43.5°F		Auto	start R8
	R8	5000ft	~43.5°		Auto	end R8
114955	P9	FL050	32°A		Auto	Profile 9 → P1060
115113	P9	060	33°A		Auto	end P9 @ FL060
	R9	060	33°A		Auto	start R9. Down sun run @ FL060
115810	R9	060	33°A		Auto	end R9
120505	P10	060	46°F		Auto	start P10 → FL130 090
121148	P10	120	46°F		Auto	End P10 @ FL120
121339	R10	120	~34.5°A		Auto	Down sun run
121941	R10	120	~34.5°A		Auto	end R10
122220			0°		Auto	
122519			0°		Auto	Sonde 3 launched.

ND3.0
Filters
-

No Filters
fitted

No
Filters
fitted.

*

CORE CHEMISTRY FLIGHT LOG

FLIGHT: B047	DATE: 02/09/2004	OPERATOR: Doug Anderson	PAGE: 1 of 1
LOCATION: N Adriatic, Italy		PROJECT: ADRIEX – flight over northern Adriatic and along the Po Valley	

GAS CYLINDER PRESSURES	N2	Argon/CO2	CO
PRE FLIGHT	1530 psi / 107 bar	2200 psi / 152 bar	690 psi / 47 bar
POST FLIGHT	psi / bar	psi / bar	psi / bar

TIME (GMT)	HEIGHT (Flight Level)	RUN #	CO SENSITIVITY (Hz/ppbV)	CO BACKGROUND (ppb)	CO BCKGRD.CNT.B (Hz)	CO CONC. (ppb V)	O3 (ppb)	NO (ppb)	NO2 (ppb)	NOx (ppb)	SO2 (ppb)			
30/08/04 13:40:53			84.30	59.91	5050.67	-	-	-	-	-	-			
Remarks: last calibration data from previous flight for comparison with today.														
02/09/04 06:23:04	ground	-	85.05	59.15	5030.95	390.903	0	43.8	17.1	60.9	5.49			
Remarks: First cal of day. Air sample pipe closed. CO cal max values : 570-523														
07::														
Remarks: Air sample pipe (ASP) closed. CO cal max values : 513-527														
07:32:34	ground	-	82.35	63.85	5257.51	237.999	7	16.31	3.53	19.83	-			
	Flow Lamp:	33.94	Press Monocr	0.76	Press Cell:	7.13	Press Cal Gas	2.51	Lamp °C	50.00	Monocr °C	25.81	PMT °C	25.73
Remarks: CO cal max values : 523-528														
07:54	ground													
Remarks: Total loss of scientific power for five minutes. All Core Chem instruments recovered OK.														
08:05:12	ground	-	90.73	61.19	5551.55	232.555	-	-	-	-	-			
	Flow Lamp:	33.93	Press Monocr	0.76	Press Cell:	7.14	Press Cal Gas	2.51	Lamp °C	50.00	Monocr °C	25.73	PMT °C	25.70
Remarks: ASP open. CO cal max values : 572-615 – too high														
08:11:08	ground	-	85.51	62.67	5375.59	224.302	14	4.79	8.23	13.16	4.72			
	Flow Lamp:	34.04	Press Monocr	0.76	Press Cell:	7.14	Press Cal Gas	2.51	Lamp °C	-	Monocr °C	-	PMT °C	-
Remarks: ASP closed. CO cal max values : 492-496														
08:15:48	ground	taxiing	85.04	63.26	5379.46	187.255	13	4.23	7.89	12.12	4.44			
Remarks: ASP closed. CO cal max values : 521-524														
08:23:18	FL050	-	84.56	63.06	5332.59	119.127	63	0.08	0.58	0.66	4.63			
Remarks: ASP now open. CO cal max values : 521-523														
08:52:08	FL150	Post P1	85.73	62.05	5320.04	74.359	65	0.04	0.24	0.28	6.04			
	Flow Lamp:	33.90	Press Monocr	0.69	Press Cell:	7.14	Press Cal Gas	2.46	Lamp °C	50.00	Monocr °C	25.50	PMT °C	25.44
Remarks: CO cal max values : 531-536														
09:24:00	FL060	Post P2	88.86	60.53	5378.83	110.009	65	-0.02	0.61	0.60	3.98			
	Flow Lamp:	34.00	Press Monocr	0.75	Press Cell:	7.15	Press Cal Gas	2.51	Lamp °C		Monocr °C		PMT °C	
Remarks: CO cal max values : 544-548 R2 started 09:23:03 approx 30 sec before end of cal														
10:10:43	100-500'	Post R6	90.99	59.43	5407.73	125.480	43	0.22	1.32	1.54	4.40			
	Flow Lamp:	33.93	Press Monocr	0.78	Press Cell:	7.13	Press Cal Gas	2.53	Lamp °C		Monocr °C		PMT °C	
Remarks: CO cal max values : 537-541														
10:56:54	800'	Into O5	90.15	58.99	5317.60	120.936	54	0.18	0.75	0.92	3.93			
	Flow Lamp:		Press Monocr		Press Cell:		Press Cal Gas		Lamp °C		Monocr °C		PMT °C	
Remarks: CO cal max values : 519-521														
11:49:07	FL050	post R8	88.74	59.37	5268.07	115.957	64	-0.01	0.85	0.84	4.23			
	Flow Lamp:	33.96	Press Monocr	0.75	Press Cell:	7.14	Press Cal Gas	2.51	Lamp °C	50.00	Monocr °C	25.33	PMT °C	25.28
Remarks: CO cal max values : 514-518														
12:15:30	FL120	into R10	87.99	59.34	5221.08	75.527	64	-0.10	0.33	0.23	5.06			
	Flow Lamp:		Press Monocr		Press Cell:		Press Cal Gas		Lamp °C		Monocr °C		PMT °C	
Remarks: CO cal max values : 518-525														
::	FL													
	Flow Lamp:		Press Monocr		Press Cell:		Press Cal Gas		Lamp °C		Monocr °C		PMT °C	
Remarks: CO cal max values :														
::	FL													
	Flow Lamp:		Press Monocr		Press Cell:		Press Cal Gas		Lamp °C		Monocr °C		PMT °C	
Remarks: CO cal max values :														
::														
Remarks: ASP closed. CO cal max values :														

Proxy Settings	Proxy address to use	Port
HTTP	151.170.32.11	8080
Secure	"	
ftp	"	
gopher	"	

ack/B046.txt = filename

PSAP B046

115720 END Profile 7 - change PSAP file ($Tr = 0.713$)

115914 - fit new filter, set $Tr = 1.000$

120013 → ~~Bap = 12.4~~ Bap = 4.7

130150 Bap = 3.6 $Tr = 0.812$.

130340 switch pump off, profiling the cloud.

133759 Bap 12.4, - 773 = ~~Tr~~ Tr , change filter, $lvls < 20$

~~134000~~

134000 running again, Bap = 17.7

1 ascii string per second PSAP time 10s (-2) = 8s fast comp
 Format: YY MM DD hh mm ss Ave Bap Tr Flow Signal Ref. ~~12s~~ will Horace

• Need harness hock on points on fwd face of rack.

PSAP	V
2.47E+00	4.81
5.50E+00	5.5
8.2500E+01	5.86
1.2600E+02	6.23
1.4100E+02	6.53
1.8800E+02	6.61
1.6240E+02	6.46
2.3800E+01	4.79

DRSU	Bap
28310	14.6
27596	12
27451	9.5
25541	2.3
18695	1.7

$0.8 \text{ E}-6 = 16442$
 $1.9 \text{ E} =$
 $2.7 = 20754$
 $0.5 = 14533$
 $2.3 = 20979$
 $7.1 = 25146$
 $4.4 = 22901$
 $8.0 = 26738$

B046

BBRs

→ 6000

Upper ~~red~~ zero - 9465 → 9485

Upper ~~red~~ clear zero - 8961 → 8986.

Lower clear zero = 8196 → 8204

Lower red zero = 8898 → 8903

Nephelometer - Pressure 951 spiking to 928mb.

when SPR = 877mb.

- DLU box with cards
- ~~or~~ TWCI box + probe

Flight Manager's Instrument Status Log

Flight No. **B.047**.....

Date**2.9.04**.....

Instrument	Fitted	Operated	Instrument	Fitted	Operated
<u>Navigation</u>			<u>Cloud Physics</u>		
INU		/	<u>Probes</u>		
GPS		/	FFSSP		✓
Satcom C		/	PCASP		✓
Satcom H		/	2D-P	X	X
<u>Thermometers</u>			2D-C	X	X
De-Iced Temp		/	Cloudscope	X	X
Non De-Iced		/	SID 1		✓
Heimann		/	SID 2	x	x
<u>Hygrometers</u>			CPI	X	
G. Eastern		/	HVPS	X	
J. Williams		/	<u>Racks:</u>		
Nevzorov	x	/	INC	x	
TWC	x	/	CCN / CNC	x	
FWVS		x	CVI		✓
<u>Radiometers</u>			<u>Aerosol</u>		
Upper Clear		/	PSAP		✓
“ Red	/	/	Nephelometer		✓
“ Silicon	/	X	AMS		✓
“ JO1D	/	X			
Lower Clear		/			
“ Red	/	/			
“ Silicon	/	X			
“ JO1D	/	X			
<u>Large Radiometers</u>					
TAFTS	X				
MARSS	X				
DEIMOS	X				
ARIES	X				
SWS / SHIM		/			
<u>Chemistry</u>					
Ozone		/			
ECGC	x				
NOX	x				
CO		/	<u>Others:</u>		
ORAC	x				
PAN		/			
PERCA	x				
WAS		/			

Flight Manager's Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B047

Instruments

1. HORACE : preflight error count on hard disk = 1, on optical = 7.
2. Neph: Pressure signal noisy and offset from SPR (50mb).
3. PSAP : output analogue voltage signal suspect, recording data (RS232) onto laptop (MREFLOT07).

Aircraft

1. Lost science pwr on engine start - lose AMS data for 1½ hrs.